

**TWENTY-FIRST YOUNG RESEARCHERS' CONFERENCE
MATERIALS SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING**

November 29 – December 1, 2023, Belgrade, Serbia

Program and the Book of Abstracts

**Materials Research Society of Serbia
&
Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA**

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Program and the Book of Abstracts

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Aim of the Conference

Main aim of the conference is to enable young researchers (post-graduate, master or doctoral student, or a PhD holder younger than 35) working in the field of materials science and engineering, to meet their colleagues and exchange experiences about their research.

Topics

Biomaterials
Environmental science
Materials for high-technology applications
Materials for new generation solar cells
Nanostructured materials
New synthesis and processing methods
Theoretical modelling of materials

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Results of the Conference

Beside printed «Program and the Book of Abstracts», which is disseminated to all conference participants, selected and awarded peer-reviewed papers will be published in journal “Tehnika – Novi Materijali”. The best presented papers, suggested by Session Chairpersons and selected by Awards Committee, will be proclaimed at the Closing Ceremony. Part of the award is free-of-charge conference fee at YUCOMAT 2024.

Sponsors

ANALYSIS
LABORATORY EQUIPMENT

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Quinuclidine thiosemicarbazone crystal structure determination: Quantum insights via Hirshfeld atom refinement and intermolecular interaction energies

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Crystal structure of quinuclidine thiosemicarbazone was determined using single crystal X-ray diffraction. During crystal structure refinement stage, conventional independent atom model (IAM) was used, as well as quantum crystallographic approach through Hirshfeld atom refinement (HAR). Two HAR approaches were tested, differing in the treatment of crystal field simulation. In the first strategy, wavefunction was obtained for the central molecule and four additional molecules involved in hydrogen bonding. In the second strategy, wavefunction was obtained for the central molecule which was placed in simulated crystal field of point and dipole charges located at positions of the surrounding molecules' atoms. In spite of the fact that HAR was performed with suboptimal diffraction data, which was collected in a routine fashion (standard resolution of $d_{\min} = 0.8 \text{ \AA}$ and room temperature), a significant improvement in the resulting geometry and refinement statistics was obtained when compared to the IAM model. HAR resulted in lower R values (2.04%; 2.06%), compared to $R=2.94\%$ obtained with IAM refinement. Additionally, during HAR the positions and displacement parameters of all H atoms were successfully refined freely. The mean values for N–H (0.999 Å; 0.993 Å) and C–H (1.081 Å; 1.080 Å) bond lengths are close to (within $\pm 0.01 \text{ \AA}$) standard values obtained with neutron diffraction (N–H=1.015 Å; C–H=1.089 Å). Results obtained indicate that HAR could yield significantly improved structural parameters of crystal structures even from routine data collection practices, which advocates its general use in small molecule crystallography. Intermolecular interaction energies were calculated with *CrystalExplorer* and *PIXEL*. Data obtained with both methods are in good agreement. The hydrogen bonded dimer with the highest interaction energy (-47 kJ mol^{-1}) is predominantly influenced by electrostatic energy contributions. The second strongest interaction (-43 kJ/mol), also mediated through a hydrogen bond, exhibits an approximately equal contribution from dispersion and electrostatic energies. Additionally, several dispersion interactions with an average energy of -15 kJ mol^{-1} are observed. In summary, the molecular packing in the crystal is of the framework type, from the energetic perspective.